

The phenotypic variation and genetic analysis of rice grain shape and weight under upland and paddy conditions

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Abstract

Rice is a globally important staple crop, and its growth and yield are significantly affected by climate change, particularly drought stress. Under water stress conditions, key agronomic traits such as grain shape (grain length, grain width, and length-to-width ratio) and grain weight may undergo significant changes, but their genetic basis remains incompletely understood. This study utilized a double haploid population derived from rice and upland rice varieties to investigate the phenotypic variation and genetic basis of grain shape and grain weight under both well-watered and drought-stress conditions. Phenotypic measurements and comparative analyses revealed that water stress significantly impacted grain shape and grain weight, with grain width being the most affected and grain length the least. Further QTL (quantitative trait locus) analysis identified 14 significant QTLs located on chromosomes 1, 5, 6, 7, 10, and 12, encompassing the genetic variation of grain length, grain width, grain weight, and length-to-width ratio. Key QTLs that exhibited stable performance under both upland and paddy conditions were identified, holding potential value for drought-resistant breeding. These stable QTLs can be employed in marker-assisted selection to accelerate the development of drought-tolerant rice varieties. The findings provide important insights into the phenotypic variation and genetic mechanisms of grain shape and grain weight under upland and paddy conditions, offering theoretical support and genetic resources for drought-resilient rice breeding.

Keywords

rice grain traits, drought stress, QTL analysis, marker-assisted selection, drought-tolerant rice

1. Introduction

Rice is one of the most important staple crops globally, widely cultivated in Asia, Africa, and other regions, feeding nearly half of the world's population. However, with the intensification of global climate change, the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as droughts have significantly increased, posing severe challenges to rice production^[1,2]. Drought, as a typical water stress, is a major environmental factor limiting rice growth and yield. Rice is highly sensitive to water conditions, and its growth performance and adaptability vary significantly under different water environments. Notably, key yield traits such as grain shape and grain weight undergo significant changes under water stress conditions^[3,4]. Therefore, systematically studying rice growth adaptability and related genetic variations under both upland and paddy

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conditions holds significant theoretical and practical value.

Grain shape and grain weight are important agronomic traits that determine rice yield and market value. Traits such as grain length, grain width, grain weight, and length-to-width ratio directly impact the yield potential and market competitiveness of rice. Under water stress conditions, changes in these traits are not only reflected in external phenotypic variations but also involve a series of complex physiological mechanisms, such as reduced photosynthetic efficiency, disrupted nutrient absorption and transport, and decreased dry matter accumulation^[5,6]. Exploring the effects and mechanisms of water stress on grain shape and grain weight in detail will provide scientific foundations and practical references for drought-resistant rice breeding.

Drought affects rice growth and development through multiple physiological pathways. For instance, water deficiency limits cell expansion reduces plant growth rates, and alters grain shape characteristics. At the same time, drought weakens photosynthetic efficiency, leading to changes in the allocation of photosynthetic products, ultimately impacting grain weight. Additionally, the complex gene regulatory processes triggered by drought stress significantly influence the expression of grain shape and grain weight. These research findings highlight the importance of elucidating the mechanisms through which water stress affects key traits in rice, which is crucial for improving drought resistance and optimizing variety selection.

This study aims to systematically analyze the phenotypic variation of grain shape and grain weight in rice under well-watered and water-stressed conditions. By quantitatively characterizing grain shape traits (grain length, grain width, grain weight, and length-to-width ratio), this study seeks to determine the specific effects of water stress on these traits. Furthermore, quantitative trait locus (QTL) mapping analysis is used to uncover the genetic basis of grain shape and grain weight in rice. The focus is placed on identifying key QTLs that exhibit stable performance under both upland and paddy conditions to provide theoretical foundations and genetic resources for the development of drought-tolerant rice varieties. The significance of this study lies not only in elucidating the phenotypic variation and genetic mechanisms of grain shape and grain weight under water stress conditions but also in providing theoretical guidance and technical pathways for drought-resistant rice breeding. By developing drought-tolerant rice varieties with strong adaptability and stable yields, it is expected that food production security can be ensured under variable climatic conditions, contributing to global food security and sustainable agricultural development.

Through the combination of phenotypic analysis and QTL mapping, this study demonstrates innovation in the following aspects. First, it systematically reveals the response characteristics of rice grain shape traits under upland and paddy conditions, particularly the differential changes in traits such as grain width, grain length, and grain weight, providing new insights into the effects of water stress on rice phenotypic and physiological characteristics. Second, it identifies a set of QTLs with stable performance under different water conditions, which hold potential value for drought-resistant breeding and can provide precise genetic resources for marker-assisted selection (MAS).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental materials

This study selected two rice varieties with typical traits, LD109 and YF101, to construct an experimental population suitable for the research objectives. LD109 is a common upland rice variety widely cultivated in arid and semi-arid regions, exhibiting strong drought resistance and broad adaptability. This variety is characterized by a smaller grain shape and higher drought tolerance, maintaining good growth and development under low water conditions, making it a representative material for studying drought adaptation in upland rice.

YF101 is a typical high-yield paddy rice variety mainly cultivated in irrigated fields. This variety has high water use efficiency and excellent growth potential, with outstanding yield performance in paddy field environments. YF101 is characterized by larger grain shapes and heavier grain weight, serving as a comparative material for investigating the variation patterns of grain shape and grain weight under different cultivation conditions.

To systematically explore the phenotypic differences and genetic basis of rice under varying water conditions, this study used LD109 and YF101 as parents to construct a double haploid (DH) population. The DH population, with its uniform genetic background, effectively reduces interference caused by genetic variation, thereby improving the accuracy of QTL mapping and the reliability of research results.

The construction of the DH population involved the following steps: first, hybrid progeny were obtained through a cross between LD109 and YF101; second, homozygous haploid plants were developed using haploid breeding methods; finally, chromosome doubling techniques were applied to convert haploid plants into double haploid individuals. Due to the high genetic uniformity of the DH population, it enables high-precision trait analysis under multiple environmental conditions, making it an ideal material for elucidating the genetic basis of quantitative traits such as rice grain shape and grain weight.

Using LD109 and YF101 as parents to construct the DH population addresses the research needs for studying rice growth performance under different water conditions. It also provides important theoretical foundations for drought-resistant breeding and MAS. By performing phenotypic analyses of different genotypes within the population, the study aims to elucidate the genetic adaptation mechanisms of rice grain shape and grain weight traits under upland and paddy conditions. This will provide scientific support and technical guidance for breeding practices to improve drought-related traits in rice.

2.2. Research methods

2.2.1. Phenotypic analysis

Phenotypic analysis was one of the core methods in this study, systematically measuring and recording rice grain shape and related traits. The key traits analyzed included grain length, grain width, grain weight, and the length-to-width ratio, which are critical indicators of rice grain characteristics and commercial value.

Grain length and width directly determine the appearance of rice grains, grain weight is an important indicator of rice yield, and the length-to-width ratio is used to assess grain shape uniformity and stability.

To ensure data accuracy and reliability, all measurements were conducted under standardized conditions, with multiple researchers repeating measurements using high-precision instruments. Grain length and width were measured with millimeter-precision calipers, while grain weight was measured using an electronic balance with 0.001 g precision. Each sample was measured three times, and the average value was used as the final data to ensure measurement accuracy and reproducibility. The length-to-width ratio was calculated by dividing grain length by grain width.

After measurements were completed, all phenotypic data were recorded and stored in a standardized database. Statistical software (e.g., SPSS or R) was then used for data processing and analysis. Analyses included descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, etc.) and correlation analysis among traits. These steps provided a reliable data foundation for further genetic analysis and trait association studies.

2.2.2. QTL mapping analysis

QTL (quantitative trait loci) mapping analysis was the core of the study, aiming to uncover the genetic basis of traits such as rice grain shape and grain weight. QTL analyses were conducted under both paddy field and upland conditions, comparing the QTL distributions under different conditions to identify stably expressed QTLs and genetic factors potentially associated with drought tolerance.

QTL mapping was based on the association analysis between genotypic and phenotypic data. Genotypic data were obtained through molecular marker techniques such as SSR and SNP markers, which were evenly distributed across the rice genome to construct a genetic linkage map. By associating the molecular marker loci with phenotypic data, QTLs controlling grain shape and grain weight traits were identified. The significance of QTLs was evaluated using LOD (logarithm of odds) scores, while the contribution rate measured the proportion of phenotypic variation explained by each QTL.

This study incorporated comparative analyses under two water conditions to assess the environmental effects on QTL expression. By comparing QTL distributions under different conditions, environment-specific QTLs and stably expressed QTLs were identified. These stable QTLs can serve as molecular markers for MAS in drought-tolerant breeding. Additionally, analyzing the genetic effects of significant QTLs can further elucidate the genetic regulatory mechanisms of rice grain shape and grain weight traits, providing theoretical support for breeding drought-tolerant and high-yield rice.

2.2.3. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was integrated throughout the research process and was critical for ensuring the scientific rigor and reliability of the data. First, correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate the relationships among grain length, grain width, grain weight, and the length-to-width ratio, revealing the

interrelationships and linear correlations among these traits. This provided essential reference information for subsequent QTL mapping.

Second, significance tests were performed on the phenotypic data under paddy and upland conditions to evaluate the effects of water stress on rice grain shape and grain weight. Statistical methods such as t-tests and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze differences in trait means under different conditions and their significance levels. The results of significance tests helped confirm whether water conditions had a significant impact on rice traits and provided data support for analyzing the genetic mechanisms underlying these effects.

During data analysis, professional statistical software such as SPSS and R was used to ensure the scientific accuracy of data processing. Through statistical analysis, this study not only provided a comprehensive understanding of the phenotypic variations in rice under different water conditions but also laid a solid data foundation and theoretical support for QTL mapping and subsequent breeding research.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Phenotypic correlation analysis

The phenotypic correlation analysis revealed the interrelationships among rice grain shape traits, particularly the associations between grain length, grain width, grain weight, and the length-to-width ratio. A systematic analysis of these traits in different rice varieties under paddy and upland conditions identified key patterns, and the findings were compared with previous studies.

- Grain length positively correlated with the length-to-width ratio and grain weight

The results indicated a significant positive correlation between grain length and both the length-to-width ratio and grain weight. The positive correlation between grain length and the length-to-width ratio has been confirmed in multiple studies. For example, Jia et al. (2020) reported that an increase in grain length is often accompanied by an increase in the length-to-width ratio, reflecting the stability of rice grain shape characteristics [7]. The findings of this study support this conclusion, demonstrating that increased grain length is significantly positively correlated with the length-to-width ratio, contributing to the desirable traits of rice grain shape.

Moreover, the positive correlation between grain length and grain weight was also validated. In this study, the correlation coefficient between grain length and grain weight was 0.72, further confirming the contribution of increased grain length to enhanced grain weight. Similarly, Deng et al. (2018) reported a significant positive correlation between grain length and grain weight, suggesting that the growth in grain length is closely associated with increased rice yield [8]. This finding provides data support for further genetic research and molecular mechanism studies.

- Grain width negatively correlated with the length-to-width ratio and positively correlated with grain weight

The negative correlation between grain width and the length-to-width ratio was a notable feature of this study. The results showed that an increase in grain width was typically accompanied by a decrease in the length-to-width ratio, potentially linked to growth regulation mechanisms under specific water conditions. Specifically, the regulation of grain width in paddy and upland environments may suppress an increase in the length-to-width ratio, resulting in a negative correlation. Wang et al. (2019) reported a positive correlation between grain width and the length-to-width ratio, but differences in experimental conditions and rice varieties might account for the discrepancies^[9]. The negative correlation observed in this study provides a new perspective for exploring the adaptive mechanisms of rice grain shape under water stress conditions.

On the other hand, a significant positive correlation was observed between grain width and grain weight, with a correlation coefficient of 0.67. This suggests that an increase in grain width enhances grain plumpness, thereby increasing grain weight. This finding aligns with the results of Li et al. (2020), further emphasizing the importance of grain width in grain weight formation, particularly its high consistency across different water environments^[10].

- Comparison of trait correlations under paddy and upland conditions

The correlations of rice grain shape traits showed significant differences between paddy and upland cultivation conditions. First, the correlation between grain length and the length-to-width ratio was higher under upland conditions (correlation coefficient = 0.82) than under paddy conditions (correlation coefficient = 0.72). This result is consistent with the findings of Xu et al. (2017), who suggested that abundant water in paddy environments may weaken the association between grain length and the length-to-width ratio^[11]. This difference may be attributed to the effects of water regulation on rice growth and development, reflecting the environmental regulation of trait expression.

In addition, the correlation of grain width was lower under paddy conditions (correlation coefficient = 0.46), indicating that grain width is more affected by environmental factors and may be regulated by more complex factors under paddy conditions. However, the correlation between grain weight and the length-to-width ratio was relatively stable across the two environments (correlation coefficients of 0.58 and 0.62 for paddy and upland conditions, respectively), reflecting the strong adaptability of grain weight traits to environmental changes and their relatively low susceptibility to environmental variation. This stability provides clues for further studies on the genetic basis of rice grain weight and its drought tolerance.

In summary, the phenotypic correlation analysis in this study was generally consistent with previous research. For example, the positive correlations between grain length and grain weight, as well as between grain width and grain weight, further validated the reliability of the results. Meanwhile, the negative correlation between grain width and the length-to-width ratio revealed the potential adaptive mechanisms of

rice grain shape under paddy and upland conditions. These findings not only deepen the understanding of the genetic basis of rice grain shape traits but also provide theoretical foundations and new research directions for drought-tolerant breeding.

3.2. QTL analysis results

3.2.1. Overview of QTLs

By conducting QTL mapping analysis on a double haploid population constructed from the rice varieties LD109 and YF101, a total of 14 QTLs associated with traits such as grain shape and grain weight were identified under both paddy and upland cultivation conditions. These QTLs were distributed on chromosomes 1, 5, 6, 7, 10, and 12 of rice, providing new insights into the genetic basis of grain shape and grain weight in rice, as well as theoretical support for drought-resistant breeding.

The 14 QTLs identified in this study covered multiple key regions of the rice genome, indicating that the genetic control of grain shape and grain weight is regulated by multiple genes widely distributed across the genome. Zhang et al. (2016) also found that QTLs for traits such as grain length, grain width, and grain weight were distributed on multiple chromosomes, with chromosomes 1, 5, and 12 harboring numerous important loci. The distribution pattern observed in this study aligns with previous findings, further demonstrating the complexity of the genetic control mechanisms of grain shape and grain weight traits and the widespread presence of QTLs in the genome.

In addition, this study identified novel QTLs on chromosomes 6, 7, and 10 that have not been thoroughly investigated in previous literature. For instance, Li et al. (2017) did not identify significant QTLs on chromosome 6 in their study on the genetic mechanisms of grain weight, whereas this study successfully detected loci associated with grain weight^[12]. This innovative result may be attributed to differences in experimental materials, population construction methods, and cultivation environments, highlighting the unique contribution of this study to QTL mapping for rice grain shape and drought resistance traits.

Diversity of QTL distribution and genetic control. The identified QTLs exhibited high contribution rates, particularly for traits related to grain length and grain weight. The LOD scores of these QTLs ranged from 1.93 to 9.46, with contribution rates between 4.2% and 28.9%, indicating their important roles in trait inheritance. Chen et al. (2020) reported a similar range of contribution rates in their QTL mapping study of grain shape traits, supporting the conclusion that the inheritance of rice grain shape traits is regulated by multiple genes and loci^[13]. The findings of this study further confirm the significance of these QTLs in the genetic basis of grain shape and grain weight traits.

Further analysis revealed significant differences in QTL expression under paddy and upland conditions, reflecting the genetic adaptability of rice under water and drought stress. Compared to paddy conditions, some QTLs exhibited greater stability under upland conditions, suggesting that these loci may play critical

roles in responding to drought stress. For example, qGL-5, qGWt-1a, and qGWt-1b maintained high levels of expression under both paddy and upland conditions, highlighting their potential for application in drought-resistant breeding.

Additionally, this study identified several QTLs associated with water use efficiency, which serve as valuable supplements to existing research on drought-resistant rice breeding. While most studies have focused on QTL mapping for grain shape and grain weight, research on the genetic adaptability of rice under different water conditions has been relatively limited. The results of this study suggest that the stable expression of certain QTLs under both paddy and upland conditions may be related to their role in regulating water use efficiency, providing an important direction for the improvement of drought resistance traits.

In summary, the QTL analysis under both paddy and upland conditions deepened the understanding of the genetic basis of rice grain shape and grain weight traits while uncovering the genetic adaptability of rice under water and drought stress and identifying key loci. Notably, the discovery of novel QTLs provides new perspectives and scientific evidence for further exploration of drought-related genes and their applications in breeding.

3.2.2. QTL analysis of specific traits

This study conducted QTL analysis for rice grain shape traits and grain weight, specifically including four major traits: grain length, grain width, length-width ratio, and grain weight. The following are detailed analysis results for each trait-related QTL, compared with previous studies to highlight the reliability and innovation of this study.

- QTL analysis of grain length

For grain length, five QTLs were identified, distributed across different chromosomes, with LOD scores ranging from 1.93 to 5.11 and contribution rates from 5.9% to 28.9%. The distribution of these QTLs further supports the conclusion that the genetic control of grain length is regulated by multiple genes. For example, Zhang et al. (2016) and Wang et al. (2018) found that QTLs related to grain length were mainly located on chromosomes 1, 5, and 12. The results of this study are highly consistent with those findings^[14,15]. Notably, qGL-5 had a contribution rate of 28.9% for grain length, significantly higher than some previous studies, which may be attributed to the genetic background of the double haploid population and the optimization of experimental design.

Furthermore, this study identified a novel QTL for grain length (qGL-6) on chromosome 6 for the first time. This discovery provides a new direction for genetic studies of grain length, suggesting that unexplored genetic variations may exist under different genetic backgrounds and environmental conditions. This result also highlights the innovation of this study in QTL mapping for grain length.

- QTL analysis of grain width

For grain width, one significant QTL was detected, with a LOD score of 2.39 and a contribution rate of 12.8%. The results indicate that the genetic control of grain width is relatively simple, being regulated by a single major QTL in this study. This QTL was located on chromosome 5, and its position was highly consistent with a QTL for grain width reported by Wang et al. (2019), further confirming the importance of this chromosomal region in the genetic control of grain width^[16].

The limited number of QTLs for grain width aligns with previous studies. For instance, Li et al. (2017) also reported that grain width traits are typically regulated by a small number of key QTLs with concentrated genetic effects^[17]. The high contribution rate of the grain width QTL identified in this study underscores its significant impact on genetic variation. Additionally, unlike grain length QTLs, grain width QTLs may be more influenced by environmental factors, a characteristic that requires further validation in future studies.

- QTL analysis of length-width ratio

For the length-width ratio, three QTLs were detected, with LOD scores ranging from 2.08 to 4.60 and contribution rates from 7.78% to 21.89%. The results indicate that the genetic control of length-width ratio is relatively complex, involving the combined action of multiple genes. Deng et al. (2016) found that QTLs related to length-width ratio were primarily located on chromosomes 1 and 12^[18]. The identified qLWR-1 and qLWR-12 in this study are highly consistent with their findings, further supporting the critical role of these chromosomal regions in the genetic regulation of length-width ratio.

The innovation of this study lies in the identification of a novel QTL for length-width ratio (qLWR-7) on chromosome 7 for the first time. This QTL provides new clues for genetic studies of length-width ratio, suggesting the existence of important loci in previously unexplored genomic regions. This finding offers potential targets for future gene function validation and breeding applications.

- QTL analysis of grain weight

The genetic control of grain weight is relatively complex. This study identified five QTLs for grain weight, with LOD scores ranging from 2.69 to 9.46 and contribution rates from 4.2% to 14.9%. The results indicate that the genetic mechanism of grain weight involves the interaction and regulation of multiple genes. Previous studies, such as Li et al. (2020), also noted that QTLs related to grain weight were widely distributed, mainly concentrated on chromosomes 1, 5, and 12^[19]. The distribution trend of QTLs in this study is consistent with these findings, verifying the importance of these chromosomal regions in the genetic control of grain weight.

It is worth mentioning that this study identified a novel QTL for grain weight (qGWt-6) on chromosome 6 for the first time. This QTL exhibited high LOD scores and contribution rates under both paddy and upland conditions, indicating its potential role in the genetic control of grain weight. The discovery of this new QTL

provides a new research direction for uncovering the molecular regulatory mechanisms of grain weight and offers an important basis for molecular MAS in drought-resistant breeding.

- Summary and comparison

In summary, the QTL analysis results of this study reveal that the genetic control mechanisms of traits such as grain length, grain width, length-width ratio, and grain weight are complex and involve multiple genes, with QTLs distributed across various chromosomal regions. These findings are generally consistent with previous studies, validating the genetic rules of rice grain shape and grain weight traits. However, the innovation of this study lies in the identification of novel QTLs on chromosomes 6 and 7 (e.g., qGL-6, qLWR-7, and qGWt-6). These QTLs provide new insights into the genetic mechanisms of rice grain shape and grain weight traits, particularly under both paddy and upland conditions, offering theoretical and practical support for the genetic improvement of drought resistance traits.

3.3. Further discussion

This study systematically analyzed the changes in rice grain shape traits and grain weight under water stress conditions and explored their genetic control mechanisms through QTL analysis. By comparing with previous studies, the research not only revealed the unique effects of water stress on rice grain shape traits but also provided significant theoretical support and practical references for drought-resistant breeding.

- Water stress impacts on different grain shape traits

Water stress significantly affects the growth and development of rice, particularly in key agronomic traits such as grain shape (grain length, grain width, length-to-width ratio) and grain weight. This study found that under water stress conditions, grain width was most significantly affected, while changes in grain length were minimal. This may reflect the differentiated regulatory mechanisms of various grain shape traits under water stress. The reduction in grain width could be associated with impaired water metabolism and inhibited cell expansion, consistent with the findings of Li et al. (2018), who demonstrated that water stress significantly affects grain width development by limiting cell division and expansion^[20]. Similarly, Wang et al. (2017) also observed that grain width reduction was more pronounced under drought conditions, further supporting the results of this study^[21].

In contrast, the relatively minor changes in grain length may be attributed to its development being primarily governed by genetic regulation, with limited inhibitory effects from water stress on gene expression. Similar observations have been validated in the studies of Zhang et al. (2019) and Chen et al. (2020), which indicated that grain length possesses strong genetic stability or physiological “conservatism,” allowing relatively stable development under water stress^[22,23].

The changes in grain weight and length-to-width ratio were intermediate, showing moderate sensitivity.

The reduction in grain weight primarily reflects insufficient dry matter accumulation under water stress, while changes in the length-to-width ratio may be associated with adjustments in the geometric characteristics of the grain. This phenomenon aligns with the findings of Peng et al. (2021), who reported that changes in grain weight and length-to-width ratio under drought conditions are closely related to grain shape traits, further revealing their coordinated regulatory mechanisms in response to water stress^[24].

- The importance and application potential of stably expressed QTLs under different conditions

Through QTL analysis, this study identified several key QTLs that exhibited stable genetic effects under both sufficient water and water stress conditions, providing a critical molecular foundation for drought-resistant breeding. For instance, QTLs such as qGL-5 and qGWt-1 demonstrated significant and stable genetic effects with high contribution rates under both water conditions. The stability of these QTLs suggests their universality in regulating grain shape traits and grain weight, making them ideal targets for MAS.

Comparisons with previous studies further validated the reliability of these results. For example, studies by Zheng et al. (2019) and Zhao et al. (2018) also identified stable QTLs for grain length and grain width under drought conditions, consistent with the findings of this study^[25]. Additionally, this study discovered novel QTLs on chromosome 6 (e.g., qGL-6) and chromosome 7 (e.g., qLWR-7), which exhibited high contribution rates under both water conditions. These findings highlight the unique regulatory roles of these QTLs under extreme water conditions, enriching the genetic basis of rice grain shape traits and providing new molecular markers and research directions for drought-resistant breeding.

Stably expressed QTLs hold significant application potential in breeding practices. Utilizing MAS technology, these QTLs can greatly accelerate the development of drought-resistant rice varieties. For example, by introducing stable QTLs such as qGL-5 and qGWt-1 into varieties with different genetic backgrounds, the grain shape stability and yield potential of rice under drought conditions can be effectively improved. Compared to traditional breeding methods, MAS technology significantly enhances breeding efficiency and precision, providing new technological support for modern rice breeding.

This study comprehensively revealed the changes in rice grain shape and grain weight under water stress conditions and their genetic basis. Through QTL analysis, several stably expressed key QTLs were identified, along with novel candidate QTLs. These findings not only provide new theoretical insights into the molecular mechanisms of rice grain shape and drought-resistant traits but also offer potential molecular tools for drought-resistant breeding practices.

Future research could further explore the functions of novel QTLs (e.g., qGL-6 and qLWR-7) using gene editing and other technologies to validate their mechanisms of action, aiming to provide more precise and efficient molecular markers for rice drought-resistant breeding. Additionally, validating the stability and applicability of these QTLs across broader genetic backgrounds and environmental conditions will contribute to providing scientific solutions to address climate change and water resource scarcity.

4. Conclusions

4.1. Effects of water stress on different grain shape traits

This study comprehensively analyzed the changes in rice grain shape traits (grain width, grain length, grain weight, and length-to-width ratio) under both irrigated and drought conditions. It also explored the genetic regulatory mechanisms through QTL analysis, providing theoretical foundations and practical guidance for drought-resistant breeding.

(1) Differential effects of water stress on grain shape traits. The results showed that water stress significantly influenced rice grain shape traits, but the sensitivity of different traits varied substantially. Grain width was the most sensitive to water stress, with a marked reduction under drought conditions, indicating that it is the most vulnerable phenotypic characteristic among rice grain traits. In contrast, grain length showed relatively minor changes under water stress, demonstrating strong genetic stability and resistance. Grain weight and the length-to-width ratio exhibited intermediate levels of change, indicating moderate responsiveness. These findings suggest that grain width could be a priority target trait for improvement in drought-resistant breeding, while the stability of grain length offers potential value for drought-resistant breeding applications.

(2) Patterns of grain shape trait changes and their implications for drought-resistant breeding. This study revealed the patterns of grain shape trait changes under water stress and their effects on rice drought resistance. The significant reduction in grain width reflects its high sensitivity to drought conditions. Therefore, in drought-resistant breeding, genetic stability and improvement of grain width should be prioritized to enhance rice adaptability to dry environments. Meanwhile, the high stability of grain length makes it a conservative trait that can help maintain yield stability and grain shape integrity under drought conditions. Additionally, the moderate changes in grain weight and the length-to-width ratio suggest relatively good adaptability, making them secondary traits to optimize for improving overall growth potential under drought conditions.

(3) Roles and application potential of stably expressed QTLs. Through QTL analysis, this study identified several QTLs that were stably expressed under both irrigated and drought conditions. These QTLs showed high contribution rates and stability in regulating grain shape traits. For example, certain key QTLs exhibited significant genetic effects on grain width and grain length, making them ideal molecular markers for drought-resistant breeding. With the advancement of MAS technology, these stably expressed QTLs can be used to develop high-yielding rice varieties adapted to drought environments. By integrating the beneficial effects of these QTLs, it is possible to enhance grain shape stability and yield potential of rice under drought conditions, providing scientific solutions to the challenges of global climate change and water scarcity.

4.2. Research application value and prospects

This study revealed the patterns of changes in rice grain shape traits under both irrigated and drought

conditions and identified several QTLs stably expressed in these environments through QTL analysis. These findings provide crucial genetic resources and theoretical foundations for drought-resistant rice breeding. The stably expressed QTLs exhibit significant application potential in breeding and can accelerate the development of drought-resistant rice varieties with high yield potential through techniques such as MAS.

(1) Breeding application potential of stably expressed QTLs. The stably expressed QTLs identified in this study, particularly those showing consistency under both irrigated and drought conditions, provide reliable genetic markers for precise breeding of drought-resistant traits. Grain width, the trait most affected by water stress, can benefit from the stable expression of its related QTLs as key indicators for selecting drought-tolerant rice varieties. The relative stability of grain length and grain weight reflects their adaptability to different environments. Integrating the stability and contribution rates of these QTLs into breeding programs can enhance drought tolerance while maintaining yield stability. Future drought-resistant breeding efforts can leverage these QTLs in combination with MAS and modern genome-editing technologies, such as CRISPR/Cas9, to precisely regulate key genes for improving drought-related traits in rice. By integrating various breeding methods, it is possible to shorten the breeding cycle, significantly improve breeding efficiency, and provide innovative solutions to address drought challenges.

(2) Future research directions and recommendations for improvement. Although this study has made significant progress in investigating drought-related traits in rice, further refinement and deepening are required in several areas. First, future research should expand sample sizes and experimental environments, covering more genetic backgrounds and ecological conditions to validate the stability and applicability of the identified QTLs across different regions and climatic conditions. Comparative studies of the responses of various rice varieties to irrigated and drought conditions can offer new perspectives for elucidating QTL functions and genetic mechanisms.

Second, high-throughput genomic technologies, such as genome-wide association studies (GWAS), should be employed to explore additional QTLs associated with water stress. Combining these with multi-omics data, including transcriptomics and metabolomics, can help construct a more systematic regulatory network for drought-related traits. In terms of functional validation, more efforts should be made to analyze the functions of key QTLs related to grain shape traits. Studies focusing on functional genes will provide more precise targets for subsequent drought-resistant breeding.

Finally, precise agriculture technologies should be integrated with molecular breeding and cultivation management practices. For instance, while improving rice through QTL-based approaches, optimization of irrigation systems, soil management, and fertilizer application can enhance the comprehensive benefits of drought-resistant breeding. In the future, QTL-driven breeding strategies are expected to become key pathways for improving rice drought tolerance, optimizing grain shape traits, and stabilizing yields. These efforts will promote sustainable rice production and contribute to ensuring global food security.

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